

Post-task Survey

Instructions: Please respond to all the questions in this survey. Mark your response with an X.

1. Familiarity

Question	None	Little	Somewhat	Familiar	Very Familiar
Context: How familiar are you with Cuban politics and social issues in general?					
Topic: How familiar are you with the 2021 Cuban Protests?					
Coverage: How familiar are you with the news coverage of the 2021 Cuban Protests in the US?					

2. System Evaluation

Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Usefulness: The system was useful to complete the task.					
Ease of Use: The system was complex or hard to use.					
Representation: The system provided an accurate representation of the narrative.					
Redundancy: The system showed many redundant events.					
Relevance: The system showed many irrelevant events.					
Depth: The number of events and details provided by the system was appropriate to solve the task.					
Reuse: I would use the system again if I had to complete a similar task.					